
VOCATIONAL EDUCATION: A STRATEGY FOR ACHIEVING NATIONAL SECURITY IN NIGERIA

BY

DABOER, GODFREY DATONG (Ph.D)
BUSINESS EDUCATION DEPARTMENT,
FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION,
PANKSHIN, PLATEAU STATE.
PHONE NUMBER: 08069651389
Email Address: daboergodfrey64@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on Vocationalization of Education for National Security in Nigeria. The roles that Vocational education play in preparing citizens to prevent, adopt and mitigate the effects of insecurity cannot be undermined Vocationalization of education is viable for industries and a prerequisite to new world technological order. It provides systematic learning for self-reliance. In a country with grave unemployment challenges, youths are at high risk of being vulnerable to political, ethnic and religious distractions which posse a major threat to National Security. Vocationalisation of education for agriculture, various trades, health services and technical training can be significant employment sources for the youths. It is against this background that this paper takes a look at some operational concepts such as vocationalization, education and national security. Therefore, in order to ensure national security through Vocationalization of education, governments should jettison the practice of playing politics with education, create more opportunities for individuals to exercise creative freedom, improve conditions of service and emphasized on quality rather than quantity of education.

Key words; Vocational, education, national security.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria has one of the largest man powers in Africa. This is evidence in the mass turn out of people that turn up during employment tests across all levels of education and disciplines. Most people that have remained on the job search for years have taken up teaching jobs mostly in primary and secondary schools. This development has further congested the education sector with people that lack specific interest in teaching and the advancement of knowledge for national development.

This critical sector is now being commercialized by the school owners, teachers and even the policy makers with unpopular reforms and misdirected priorities. The teachers are more comfortable with abandoning the work at the expense of their monetary gains. School owners have made their institutions business centres than conducive teaching and learning environments, this is a common practice at the secondary level. No wonder, there are more students awaiting entry into tertiary education than there are enough schools to effectively cater for their educational needs. Most of these students can hardly demonstrate the minimum task expected at that level; there are more graduates of various levels of education than there are people with productive, functional knowledge and skills required by industries for self-actualization.

Education is supposed to facilitate social and economic progress, improve functional and analytical ability thereby opening up opportunities for individuals and also groups to achieve greater access to labour markets and livelihoods (Alfred, 2010). A better educated labour force is essential if we are to meet the labour supply requirements of faster growth. Education is not only an instrument of enhancing efficiency but also an effective tool of widening and augmenting democratic participation and upgrading the overall quality of individual and societal life (Nwana, 2000). Any country with higher and better levels of knowledge and skills respond more effectively and promptly to challenges and opportunities of globalization. Nigeria is supposed to be in transition to a knowledge based economy and its competitive edge will be determined by the abilities of its people to create, share and use knowledge more effectively. This transition will require the development of workers into knowledge workers who will be more flexible, analytical, and adaptable and multi skilled (Ajai, 2007). In the new knowledge economy, the skill sets will include professional, managerial, operational, behavioural, inter personal and inter functional skills (Ajai, 2007). The issues highlighted have put Nigeria in a high risk economic statute with angry youths constituting security menace.

OPERATIONAL CONCEPTS: VOCATIONALIZATION

Vocationalization means training in some specific vocation or occupation. It is also seen as the combination of general education and vocational education such as learning trade, skill or occupation to enter into real world of work. It is a practical segment of education targeted at skill acquisition. According to Danko (2006), vocationalization of education is an education programme that prepares students mainly for occupations requiring manipulative skills in such fields as Agriculture, Business Education, Home Economics, Painting, Decorating and others. Vocationalization of education is organized to secure confidence and experience by the individual students. Vocationalization is initiating intellectual training and solid ability to solve problems. This means that Vocational and Technical Education scheme should contain humanistic and technological components on the one hand, and training opportunities geared towards problem solving on the other.

EDUCATION

Education is the process of acquiring more knowledge in order to be more beneficial to self and society at large. When someone attends higher education, he or she should be able to perform higher task towards the improvement of self and contribute more meaningfully to society. According to Hornby (2000), education is the systematic training and instruction (especially of the young in schools and colleges), knowledge and abilities, development of character and mental powers resulting from such training.

Education whether formal or informal entails imparting knowledge, skills competence, to enable the learner acquire basic mental knowledge and abilities from such training, that develops the individuals character that may lead to attitudinal changes. Not just that, it can enable the learner utilize appropriate tools to achieve set goals and objectives.

NATIONAL SECURITY

National Security can be seen differently based on a nation's peculiar security challenges which are a function of its social, economic and political circumstances. National security also borders dimensions such as jobs, water and food security, good housing, adequate social amenities and good governance; otherwise a national security policy would be of no use to the unemployed, hungry and deprived citizens that constitute the majority of the population. While some people see security issues as issues that pose threats to lives and properties, others see it in terms of a nation's military capabilities or the struggle to overcome internal and external aggression (Ramala, 2012).

Therefore, a country's national security may be viewed from its freedom from military threats or political coercion. National security is the physical protection and defense of the citizens and territorial integrity, promotion of the economic wellbeing and prosperity of a nation. According to Alfred (2010), national security is a situation that provides a safe and secure environment that promotes the attainment of national interests and those of foreign partners. National security can also be construed as the pursuit of high standard of living, the promotion and protection of core values, dignity, pride and the fundamental rights, as well as the entrenchment of social justice to engender peace, unity and development of the citizenry (Ramala, 2012). Based on the these viewpoints, National security enhances the following advantages;

1. Economic prosperity,
2. Peace and social justice at individual and societal level,
3. Attainment of national interest and those of foreign partners,
4. Better standard of living through the provision of social amenities like water supply, power supply, good roads, good schools, food sufficiency, good hospitals, functional infrastructure, decent housing, effective public transportation system, etc.
5. Freedom from stress and psychological tension for daily livelihood.

According to Zhao and Seibert (2006), National security means national peace and stability, national consciousness, national defense and self-reliance. Alfred (2010) in Daboer and Dashe (2012), averred that security entails anything that gives or assures safety, free from danger, free from fear or doubt, not likely to fall or give away, stable, assured and certain.

Obama (2010) emphasized that national security is the requirement to maintain the survival of a country through the use of economic diplomacy and political power. Indeed, it encompasses a broad range of facets, all which impinge on the economic security of the nation and the values espoused by the national security.

OBJECTIVES OF VOCATIONALIZATION OF EDUCATION

The worldwide constant innovative changes have shown that the future is unpredictable especially as it concerns education, technology, skills and competencies which are imperatives of economic, social and political mobility, growth and development. Vocationalization of education is aimed at preparing the learner for entry into employment in his or her chosen career, meet the manpower need for the society, increase the option available to each student, motivating force to enhance all types of learning and enable the learner to wisely elect a career (Danko, 2006). Based on these aims, one could derive the importance of vocational and technical education as the provider of employment and poverty alleviation.

The objectives of vocational education as identified by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) in its National Policy on Education are:-

- i. To provide trained man power in applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advanced craft and technical level.
- ii. To provide the technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agricultural, commerce and economic development, and
- iii. To give training and impart necessary skills to individuals who shall be self-reliance economically. Both the objectives of entrepreneurship and vocational education are directed towards training of students for self-reliance.

VOCATIONALIZATION OF EDUCATION FOR NATIONAL SECURITY

Vocationalization of education is undoubtedly a very important step in the Nigerian socio- economic system. It develops occupational competence and teaches those skills which enable an individual earn a living thereby controlling his tendency for aggression, which is a major threat to National security. The National Policy on Education (2004), define vocational education as that aspect of education which leads to the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge. Vocationalization of education is viable for industries and a prerequisite to new world technological order which provides the means against social disequilibrium and enhance social order especially in an unemployed society like Nigeria. It provides the necessary skills for leaving experience meant to be impacted to an individual systematically in order to get him/her adequately equipped for a good employment for self-reliance.

Aremu (2010) views vocational training as utilitarianism and that it is a concept of reorganizing the importance of labour, training someone in his appropriate field and for him to substantially be self-independent and contribute to social order and the overall good of the nation. For this reason, any nation or country whose population is largely dependent or unemployable is prone to security threats as a hungry man they say is an angry man.

CHALLENGES OF VOCATIONALIZATION OF EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

Vocationalization of education has been bedeviled by serious challenges especially in the recent times due to Nigeria political stand point which does not favour mass developmental strategy in the education sector; unemployment/underemployment being almost at the grave state with little tangible effort to circumvent the situation. Some challenges observed by Okwor (2009) and Manfred & Jennifer (2004) are still highly noticeable and are worth mentioned here:

1. Inappropriate workable policies and strategies that supports the development of vocational education.
2. Lack of continuity in vocational technical education and training.

3. Lack of coherent guidance and counselling system which will help to put students in proper career path.
4. Inadequate development of vocational institutions through adequate equipment and use of qualified trainers.
5. Inadequate awareness through image building, vocational attractiveness and participation in vocational technical education in Nigeria.
6. Lack of ambitious and realistic goals that will enable Nigeria to be the most competitive in terms of technical advancement.
7. Inability to create and sensitize the Nigerian populace on needs and vision of vocational technical education.
8. Maintaining approved school age in order to pave way for physical and mental maturity required for the acquisition of vocational skills.
9. Inadequate investment in quality vocational education system owing to lukewarm attitude of government at various levels.
10. Inappropriate measures in tackling the issues of insufficient and lack of up-to-date data for assessment of progress in vocational technical education.
11. Lack of stringent measures for proper and efficient execution of policies regarding vocational and technical education.
12. Problem in the adoption of uniform standard and certification in vocational education at all levels.

These issues mentioned above by Manfred and Jennifer is fundamental as their economic effects for the country's development cannot be over emphasized. The greatest weakness in the vocationalization of education is disjointed training and lack of continuity of the programme from primary school level to tertiary school level and no-the-job training (Sekuk, 2010). There is urgent need for continuity in any programme or training in vocational education as good policies and goals do starts from the infancy stage to fully completed and evaluated stage without creating gaps along the line (Olaitan, 1999).

During 1970s and 1980s for instance, primary school pupils and secondary school students were encouraged through government policy to undertake handcraft and other skill acquisition tasks themselves as part of continuous assessment during a prescribed period of time (Sekuk, 2010). Today, this most important practice has gone into extinction with no effort towards a better substitute in the face of increasing challenges. This attitude causes a dead of vocational education at that point.

PROBLEMS OF NATIONAL SECURITY

According to Ramala (2012), Nigeria would have been a secured country but for the following problems;

1. Corruption: This has created an unending vicious circle of poverty, deprivation, greed and exploitation causing the less opportune youth aggressiveness;
2. Unemployment: Many people are unemployed or underemployed and there is no hope of the situation changing in the nearest future because of the increasing challenges of the labour market, which has become unattainable to the less opportune youth due to their circumstances. This can cause anger especially where those in high places are not better of;
3. Lack of required facilities to support effective learning in public schools. These can cause the feelings of deprivation which ultimately undermines national security.

4. Distractions to socio-political stability, this can result from crisis among the elites or elite fragmentation. The elites are unfortunately engaged in endless competition and the pursuit of narrow selfish interests, at the expense of national unity and integration.
5. Bad governance: This is the effect of four (4) mentioned above.

PROBLEMS MILITATING AGAINST VOCATIONALIZATION OF EDUCATION FOR NATIONAL SECURITY

A study of the prevailing vocational education activities and the challenges of insecurity in Nigeria reveal the following problems militating against vocationalization of education for national security.

- i. Most youths in Nigeria that have never been able to attend any formal school before are now craving for education in Colleges. This population who are mostly migrants from the rural areas are difficult to teach as some of them are not ready to go through the rigorous teaching and learning exercise with patience.
- ii. Expansion in the number of students for vocational education without corresponding expansion in facilities required for vocationalization of education is taking place and the political class in flying capital on private jets. The multiplier effect of this capital flight is grave on vocationalization of education for national security.
- iii. Gross infrastructural inadequacy is a major challenge as well, vocationalization of education is dependent on effective infrastructural systems such as electricity. The epileptic nature of power supply has made it rather difficult for modern machines to be used flexibly and efficiently by the education sectors.
- iv. Lack of parental guidance as most parents do not guide their wards to take up courses in Vocational and Technical Education programme due to negative value attached to vocational education in Nigeria.

Thus, more students are joining higher education and looking for vertical mobility without the requisite skills and knowledge for social mobility. This situation has posed a great problem of vocationalization of education for national security.

CONCLUSION

Nigeria has explored several ways to combating national security problems that have made the country almost ungovernable. The funny aspect of it is that the situation keeps aggravating despite increased investment in security apparatus and diplomacy.

Quality vocationalization of education develops functional knowledge, skills and motivation to guarantee self-reliance by providing employment, reduce poverty, build self-esteem and create a sense of belonging in the minds of individuals thereby ensuring national security of the nation.

The non-acceptance of vocational education and training as a means of intervention in the normal course of development by some Nigerians has brought a setback in our national security, which must be addressed.

National security is not just a matter of military combat; it is quality raising and capacity building through scientific education. Thus education plays an important role in the process of national security.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to ensure national security through vocationalization of education, the following recommendations must not be taken for granted.

1. Governments should jettison the practice of playing politics with education, create more opportunities for individuals to exercise creative freedom and make the environment safe for learning, and investment-friendly by providing social amenities, especially power supply and good roads. These are too critical to be given lip service.
2. Vocational education should commence from the grassroots, made qualitative and practical oriented with appropriate support mechanisms such as finance and effective supervision.
3. The development of respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms should be enshrined in our curriculum, especially religious education. Government should stop financing pilgrimages and use the funds to vocationalize education. Religion should be made a personal affair.
4. There is urgent need for continuity in any programme or training in vocational education as good policies and programmes in Nigeria do not start from the infancy stage to complete and evaluation stage without creating gap along the line.
5. The political class should be more patriotic by investing in real sectors that support industrialization rather than purchasing private jets and contributing to capital flight, not responding to educational needs of the country genuinely thereby forcing continuous strikes in the education sector.

REFERENCES

- Ajai, O. (2007). *Quality and Quantity Assurance: The Imperative for Improved Teachers' Quality*. A paper presented at the 20th Annual Conference of Curriculum organization of Nigeria. Abia State University Uturu.
- Albert, S. (1985). *Nurturing the Entrepreneurial Spirit*. U.S.A. Ohio State University.
- Alfred E. (2010). *Quality Assurance in Nigeria Education System in the 21st Century*. Federal College of Education, Amatu, Journal of School of Vocational Education. Vol.5
- Aremu, M. (2010). *Small and Medium Scale Enterprises As A Means of Employment Generation and Capacity Building in Nigeria*. A paper presented at the International Conference on Management and Enterprise Development on "Intellectuals and New Strategies for Sustainability Development of the Third World" Held at Conference Centre, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria, October 5th – 8th.
- Babalola, Y.A. and Tihamiyu, R. (2012). *Peace and Security in Nigeria: The Role of Business Education*. A paper presented at the 17th Annual National Conference of National Association of Women in Colleges of Education (WICE) at Federal College of Education (Technical) Umuze.
- Barack Obama: *National Security*: www.wikipedia free encyclopedia. Retrieved 21/03/2014.
- Danko, A.I. (2006). *Entrepreneurship Education for Vocational and Technical Education Students* – second edition. Pp. 2-3.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria, (2004). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: Federal Government Press.

- Manfred & Jennifer W. (2004). *Vocational Education and Training Key to the Future*. Greece. Colibri ltd Manfre.
- Obama, (2010), In Daboer & Dashe (2012), *Quality Education for National Stability: Matter Answering*. A Compendium of the 5th National Conference of COEASU College of Education, Gindiri 2, 1 – 14.
- Okoro, O.M. (1993). *Principles and Methods in Vocational and Technical Education*. Nsukka University Trust Publication.
- Olaitan, et al (1999). *Curriculum Development and Management in Vocational and Technical Education*. Caps Publishers International Limited, Onitsha.
- Ramala, M. (2012). *National Security Challenges and the Way Forward*. Retrieved on 23/03/2013 from www.security/wiki.
- Sekuk, R.T. (2010). *An X-ray of Possible Business Students of Vocational and Technical Education can Engage in: The Counselling Intervention*, Pankshin journal of Vocational Education Vol.5.
- Usioboh, S.A. (2007). *The Education Reform Agenda – Challenges and Prospects for Tertiary Education in Nigeria*: Journal of National Association of Professional Secretarial Staff of Nigeria. Vol. 12 (5) 54.
- Zhao, H. and Selbert, S. (2006). *The Big Five Personality Dimensions and Entrepreneurial Status*. A Meta Analytical Review, Journal of Applied Psychology.
- Zhao, H. and Selbert, S. (2006). In Daboer & Dashe (2012), *The Big Five Personality Dimensions and Entrepreneurial Analytical Review*, Journal of Applied Psychology.